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Revelation of the Hollowness of War and Sham Higher Love by George Bernard Shaw in His Play: Arms and the Man

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For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>**Sangeeta Chauhan**Assistant Professor
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Abstract George Bernard Shaw represents his views on the glory of war and higher love in his play Arms and the Man through the character of captain Bluntschli. Captain Bluntschli is the mouthpiece of George Bernard Shaw in this play. Raina Petkoff, the heroine of the play is betrothed with Major Sergius Saranoff, who is a reputed officer in the Bulgarian army. Raina Petkoff and captain Sergius love each other. Raina Petkoff is extremely emotional and romantic for Sergius. She is impressed by Sergius' romanticism and way of fighting in the war. Raina Petkoff glorifies to captain Sergius by saying him as her super hero. Captain Bluntschli, who is fought against Bulgarian army tells the reality of the war to Raina Petkoff. Here, George Bernard Shaw shows the funny revelation of the glory of war and higher love.

Keywords Hollowness of War, Sham Higher Love, George Bernard Shaw, Arms and the Man.

Introduction

Arms and the Man is a satirical play written by George Bernard Shaw. George Bernard Shaw was an Irish playwright, author, literary critic, social propagandist, political activist, and the winner of the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1925. Shaw began his literary career as a novelist, and he decided to write plays in order to illustrate his criticism of the English stage. His plays were popular for their biting wit and humour. Arms and the Man was one of Shaw's first commercial successes. Arms and the Man humourously exposes the futility of war and the hypocrisies of human nature.

Objective of study

This play has been proved a milestone in the field of English Literature for other playwrights. Here, George Bernard Shaw strikes on the glorification of the war and higher love in this play. Shaw describes the event of November 1885 in the play. There's happening a war between two nations Bulgaria and Serbia. Mr. Petkoff is a major in the Bulgarian army. Sergius Saranoff is a Bulgarian major, dashing and romantic figure, but ultimately a foolish soldier who is more interested in appearances and self aggrandizement than in actual military skills.

Review of Literature

George Bernard Shaw awakens to humans for the hollowness of war and sham higher love in this play. Shaw describes the event of November 1885 in the play. George Bernard Shaw's play Arms and the Man is set during the Serbo-Bulgarian war in 1885. Captain Bluntschli the Swiss mercenary fights against the Bulgarian army, while Bulgarian cavalry led by Sergius Saranoff fights against the Serbian army. Bulgarian army wins in the battle and Major Sergius Saranoff is welcomed warmly by Mr. and Mrs. Petkoff. Catherine Petkoff, mother of Raina Petkoff kisses to Sergius Saranoff and appreciate him.

Main Text

Catherine: You look superb-splendid. The campaign has improved you. Everybody here is mad about you. We were all wild with enthusiasm about that magnificent cavalry charge.
Sergius (with grave irony): Madam: it was the cradle and the grave of my military reputation.(Shaw 30)
Captain Bluntschli is a Swiss Soldier, but he fights with the Serbian army against Bulgarian army. Captain Bluntschli fights only for earning money as a practical person.

He doesn't believe in the glory of war and higher love. Captain Bluntschli keeps chocolates in his bag instead of cartridges. As he says to Raina Petkoff in the play,
Man: I've no ammunition. What use are cartridges in battle? I always carry chocolate instead; and I finished the last cake of that yesterday.

Raina: Chocolate! Do you stuff your pockets with sweets-like a schoolboy-even in the field? (Shaw 12)

Actually Bulgarian army wins the battle not because of Sergius' forceful leadership in the war; but because of Serbian's foolishness to use wrong ammunition during the war. Raina Petkoff appreciates the bravery of her fiancé. She praises for the glory of Sergius' bravery in the battle field, when she talks with captain Bluntschli. She says her hero to Sergius before captain Bluntschli during her conversation.

Raina: That is a photograph of the gentleman- the patriot and hero- to whom I am betrothed.

Man (looking at it): I'm really very sorry. (looking at her.) Was it fair to lead me on? (He looks at the portrait again.) Yes: that's him: not a doubt of it. (He stifles a laugh.) (Shaw 15)

When Raina Petkoff praises highly about the characteristics of her fiancé before captain Bluntschli, captain Bluntschli is very shocked and make fun of her. Raina Petkoff says that her fiancé is hero because he is the very first man who goes out for the battle with his army. Captain Bluntschli keeps to converse with Raina Petkoff.

Raina: Ugh! But I don't believe the first man is a coward. I believe he is a hero!

Man (goodhumoredly): That's what you'd have said if you'd seen the first man in the charge today.

Raina (breathless): Ah, I knew it! Tell me-tell me about him.

Man: He did it like an operatic tenor-a regular handsome fellow, with flashing eyes and lovely moustache, shouting a war-cry and charging like Don Quixote at the windmills. We nearly burst with laughter at him; but when the sergeant ran up as white as a sheet, and told us they'd sent us the wrong cartridges, and that we couldn't fire a shot for the next ten minutes, we laughed at the other side of our mouths. I never felt so sick in my life, though I have been in one or two very tight places. And I hadn't even a revolver cartridge- nothing but chocolate. We'd no bayonets- nothing. Of course, they just cut us to bits. And there was Don Quixote flourishing like a drum major, thinking he'd done the cleverest thing ever known, whereas he ought to be court- martialed for it. Of all the fools ever let loose on a field of battle, that man must be the very maddest. He and his regiment simply committed suicide- only the pistol missed fire, that's all. (Shaw 14-15)

When captain Bluntschli takes shelter in Raina's room through the opening window of balcony, Raina Petkoff gets fear. Captain Bluntschli scares her as he will shoot to Raina Petkoff, if she shout for her help from the Serbian fugitive soldier. Raina Petkoff is scared and does not tell anyone about the man hiding behind the curtains. When Louka, the maid servant and Raina's mother mother visit one by one and suspect that someone is in Raina's room, Raina denies and speaks lie to both of them. Although she took help of her mother for escaping the Serbian army captain Bluntschli, yet she hides his presence in the very beginning. Raina Petkoff talks to captain Bluntschli because they both are awakening in the midnight. After the confession of keeping chocolates instead of cartridges in his bag by captain Bluntschli, Raina Petkoff gives him nickname as the chocolate cream soldier.

Raina: You are my enemy; and you are at my mercy. What would I do if I were a professional soldier?

Man: Ah, true, dear young lady: you're always right. I know how good you have been to me: to my last hour I shall remember those three chocolates creams. It was unsoldierly; but it was angelic. (Shaw 16)

When captain Bluntschli criticizes to Major Sergius Saranoff who is Raina's fiancé, Raina Petkoff gets angry and says him to run away from her room. She says to the fugitive soldier that she will go out on the balcony and see whether it is safe for him to climb down into the street. Captain Bluntschli denies to go down from the pipe, because it's too hard to get down from the pipe. He accepts his defeat and surrender himself before Raina Petkoff. After seeing the polite behaviour of the fugitive, Raina Petkoff fulfills with mercy and says to him.

Raina (disarmed by pity): Come, don't be disheartened. (She stoops over him almost maternally: he shakes his head.) Oh you are a very poor soldier-a chocolate cream soldier. Come, cheer up: it takes less courage to climb down than to face capture-remember that.

Man (dreamily, lulled by her voice): No, capture only means death; and death is sleep-oh, sleep, sleep, sleep, undisturbed sleep! Climbing down the pipe means doing something- exerting myself-thinking! Death ten times over first. (Shaw 16-17)

We find out that Raina Petkoff is highly impressed by the humble behaviour of the fugitive soldier. Captain Bluntschli wants to run away from Raina's room, so that nobody will say her traitor. He tries to go outside from the window, but there's a terrible burst of firing in the street beneath. Raina Petkoff stops him to go down from the window. When captain Bluntschli says to Raina when he will open the shutters she should keep away from the window, because Bulgarian soldiers are searching him; and they shoot him definitely. Raina Petkoff become very generous for him and says.

Raina (clinging to him): They're sure to see you: it's bright moonlight. I'll save you-oh, how can you be so indifferent? You want me to save you, don't you?

Man: I really don't want to be troublesome. (She shakes him in her impatience.) I am not indifferent, dear young lady, I assure you. But how is it to be done? (Shaw 17-18)

We find out that Raina Petkoff gets emotions in her heart for the fugitive soldier captain Bluntschli during their conversation at midnight. She notices the good character of captain Bluntschli. It's captain Bluntschli who exposes Raina's idealized views of war and love. He is a realistic who sees the absurd romanticism of war, unlike the aristocratic volunteers who are untrained and idealistic. Bluntschli is a professional soldier trained in waging war in a highly efficient, businesslike manner.

Bluntschli's presence and engagement to Raina create conflict with Sergius, Raina's former fiancé who is romanticized yet ultimately flawed, character. Sergius Saranoff flirts with Louka in Raina's absenc, the maid servant of Petkoff family. He has physical relationship with her. Louka is very cunning and knows how to entrapped to Sergius in her love bond. When Sergius comes back from the war to meet Raina Petkoff and her family members, he seeks the chance to flirt with Louka.

Sergius: I am surprised at myself, Louka: what would Sergius, the hero of Slivnitza, say if he saw me now? What would Sergius, the apostle of the higher love, say if he saw me now? What would the half dozen Sergiuses keep popping in and out of this handsome figure of mine say if they caught us here? (Letting go her hand and slipping his arm dexterously round her waist.) Do you consider my figure handsome, Louka?

Louka: Let me go, sir. I shall be disgraced. (She struggles: he holds her inexorably.) Oh, will you let go?

Sergius (looking straight into her eyes): No

Louka: Then stand back where we can't be seen. Have you no common sense?

Sergius: Ah, that's reasonable. (He takes her into the stable yard gateway, where they are hidden from the house.) (Shaw 37)

Georget Bernard Shaw challenges the romantic idealism through the character of captain Bluntschli in the play Arms and the Man. Bluntschli is a Swiss mercenary fighting for the Serbian army, a professional soldier who is skilled in warfare and emotionally sophisticated. Raina Petkoff is fallen in love with Major Sergius Saranoff blindly. She kisses Sergius' portrait even in his absence. Raina and Sergius believe in the higher and idealized love. After returning of Sergius Saranoff from the battlefield to Raina's house, they both talk romantically with each other.

Raina (placing her hands on his shoulder as she looks up at him with admiration and worship): My hero! My king.

Sergius: My queen! (He kisses her on the forehead with holy awe.)

Raina: How I have envied you, Sergius! You have been out in the world, on the field of battle, able to prove yourself there worthy of any woman in the world; whilst I have had to sit at home inactive,- dreaming-useless-doing nothing that could give me the right to call myself worthy of any man.

Sergius: Dearest, all my deeds have been yours. You inspired me. I have gone through the war like a knight in a tournament with his lady looking on at him!

Raina: And you have never been absent from my thoughts for a moment. Sergius, I think we two have found the higher love. When I think of you, I feel that I could never do a base deed or think an ignoble thought.

Sergius: My lady, and my saint! (Clasping her reverently.)

Raina (returning his embrace): My lord and my g-

Sergius: Sh-sh! Let me be the worshipper, dear. You little know how unworthy even the best man is of a girl's pure passion. (Shaw 35-36)

Bluntschli initially changes Raina's romantic notions but their interaction leads to a genuine connection and ultimately a marriage. Raina Petkoff's notion for higher love is totally broken, when she comes to know about Sergius Saranoff's physical relationship with Louka. After coming captain Bluntschli in her house, Raina feels happy and calls him as her chocolate cream soldier. There's a deep argument among captain Bluntschli, Raina Petkoff, Louka and Sergius. Sergius blames her for deceiving him in his absence. Raina Petkoff gets angry and exposes to Sergius before all people.

Sergius: A hollow sham, I say. Would you have come back here if nothing had passed between you, except at the muzzle of your pistol? Raina is mistaken about our friend who

was burnt. He was not my informant.

Raina: Who then? (Suddenly guessing the truth) Ah, Louka! My maid, my servant! You were with her this morning all that time after- after,-Oh, what sort of god is this I have been worshipping! Do you know that I looked out of the window as I went upstairs, to have another sight of my hero; and I saw something that I did not understand then. I know now that you were making love to her.(Shaw 69)

Raina Petkoff tries to prove herself the true beloved of major Sergius Saranoff before captain Bluntschli. Captain Bluntschli makes fun of her and says that he doesn't believe in higher love and also the ideal war as well. According to him, a soldier wants to save his life even in the battle field. When Raina Petkoff praises higher love and idealistic war to captain Bluntschli, at this he replies her the satisfactory answer.

Bluntschli: My dear young lady, don't let this worry you. Remember: I am a soldier. Now what are the two things that happen to a soldier so often that he comes to think nothing of them? One is hearing people tell lies (Raina recoils): the other is getting his life saved in all sorts of ways by all sorts of people.

Raina (rising in indignant protest): And so he becomes a creature incapable of faith and of gratitude.

Bluntschli (making a wry face): Do you like gratitude? I don't. If pity is akin to love, gratitude is akin to the other thing. (Shaw 55-56)

The crucial conversation between Bluntschli and Sergius takes place in Act 3, involves Bluntschli's pragmatic and humours approach to love and war, contrasting sharply with Sergius romanticized and self-serving ideals. Bluntschli, a Swiss Soldier appears initially as a chocolate cream soldier to Raina, contrasting with Sergius' idealized image of a Heroic warrior. Bluntschli's practical approach to war and love challenges Sergius romanticized notions about war and love. Sergius' feeling threatened by Bluntschli's feeling with Raina Petkoff, challenges him to a duel, but Bluntschli cleverly avoids it by revealing his true feelings for Raina and his wealth.

Sergius: And how ridiculous! Oh, war! War! War! The dream of patriots and heroes! A fraud, Bluntschli, a hallow sham, like love.

Raina (outraged): Like love! You say that before me.

Bluntschli: Come, Saranoff: That matter is explained.(Shaw 69)

Now Sergius focuses on his own image and social status, undergoes a transformation as he realizes the limitations of his romantic ideals and the importance of true love.

Sergius (cynically): Raina: our romance is shattered. Life is a farce.

Bluntschli (to Raina, goodhumoredly): You see: he is found himself out now.

Sergius: Bluntschli: I have allowed you to call me a blockhead You may now call me a coward as well. I refuse to fight you. (Shaw 69-70)

Bluntschli views war as a profession and prioritize survival and practicality over romantic notions of honour and courage. Captain Bluntschli exposes the futility of war and sham higher love in front of Sergius.

Bluntschli- ...I am a professional soldier. I fight when I have to and am very glad to get out of it when I haven't to. You are only an amateur: You think fighting is an amusement.

Sergius: ...I could no more fight with you than I could make love to an ugly woman: You have no magnetism: You are not a man, you are a machine.

Bluntschli (apologetically): Quite true, quite true. I always was that sort of chap. I am very sorry. But now you have found that life is not a farce, but something quite sensible and serious. (Shaw 70)

The play ends with Sergius' marrying Louka, and Bluntschli's marrying Raina, signifying a shift away from romanticized ideals and towards a more realistically pragmatic understanding of love and war. In this play George Bernard Shaw uses the title of Arms and the Man ironically, suggests that war is not about glory and heroism, but about the messy often meaningless.

Conclusion

George Bernard Shaw strikes on the glorification of the war and higher love through the character of captain Bluntschli. Captain Bluntschli dispels the myth of war to Raina Petkoff and Sergius Saranoff. According to him war is only a profession for the soldier and nothing more. George Bernard Shaw shows that war is only a waste of time and resources, with little real impact or lasting benefit. In Arms and the Man captain Bluntschli is a pragmatic and skilled soldier who clarifies Raina's idealized romantic notions of war and higher love. Thus I can say that George Bernard Shaw exposes the reality of war and higher love by his famous play Arms and the Man through the character sketch of captain Bluntschli. Arms and the Man is a true revelation about the reality of war and love, and George Bernard Shaw has been succeed in showing the hollowness of the idealized views about the higher love and idealistic war.

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